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**METROLOGY
PARTNERSHIP**

Metering uncertainty for custody transfer of hydrogen for transport, heat, and storage

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Summary

The total quantity and energy delivered through a metering point in a gas grid is calculated using simple formulas that sum the increments measured at regular time intervals. These calculations are described in international standards (e.g., ISO 15112 and EN 1776) and guidelines (e.g., OIML R140). The uncertainty structure of the measurement results that enter in these calculations is quite complex and contains a lot of dependencies. These dependencies arise in part due to the fact that the same equipment is used throughout a metering point, and partly due to fluctuations in environmental conditions (e.g., flow rate, composition, pressure, temperature) give rise to dependencies.

The evaluation of the associated measurement uncertainty should thus appreciate these dependencies. In the project in the European Partnership for Metrology programme, “Metrology for the hydrogen supply chain”, the underlying assumptions of these uncertainty evaluations were revisited and reworked to be more adequate. The dependence of measurement results from, e.g., the same flow meter and gas chromatograph will be assessed for correlations, along with other effects such as the chosen mathematical approximation of the totalisation integral and fluctuations in flow rate and gas quality [1].

This report illustrates methodological approaches for evaluating measurement uncertainties through selected case studies along the supply chain. The aim of this is to demonstrate how the extended methods for evaluating measurement uncertainty can be applied and how dependencies between measurement results can be evaluated and taken up in custody transfer.

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1 Introduction

Measurements along the supply chains for natural gas, biomethane and hydrogen are made for a variety of purposes, but mostly for

- custody transfer
- billing
- health, safety and environment
- process control

The first three application areas require measurement results that are metrologically traceable. Often, the reference to which these measurement results are made traceable is the *Système International d'unités* (SI). The units in the SI, like K, MPa, cmol mol^{-1} , $\text{m}^3 \text{h}^{-1}$ are the ultimate references for measuring temperature, pressure, amount fraction (mole fraction) and volume flow rate, respectively [2]. Results, made traceable to the same reference can be compared and usefully combined, e.g., in subsequent calculations such as in the determination of the mass, volume or energy delivered over a specified time period [3, 4]. For process control, using a local measurement standard or reference may do to detect (subtle) changes in processes. This report deals with measurement result that are metrologically traceable, and unless stated otherwise, it is assumed that the reference is the SI.

To assess conformity with, e.g., contractual obligations, legislation, regulation, documentary standards, a measurement result should not only have a value (in the language of the *Guide to the expression of Uncertainty in Measurement* (GUM) an *estimate* [5]), but also a statement of measurement uncertainty. It can be a standard uncertainty, expanded uncertainty, a coverage interval or in any other form. In the industry, the standard uncertainty and expanded uncertainty are most widely used, where usually the expanded uncertainty is obtained by multiplying the standard uncertainty by a coverage factor $k = 2$. In many data transfers, the uncertainty is omitted or implied. For the results presented in this report, that does not matter; there is measurement uncertainty, and it shall be evaluated [3, 4, 6] and when making decisions, it should be considered [7]. Such consideration can also be setting a cap on the measurement uncertainty and sharing the risks equally between the parties involved in a conformity assessment. The way in which measurement uncertainty is taken into account during conformity assessment is called a “decision rule” and for example laboratories are required to report such rules [8].

An uncertainty budget is a list of sources of measurement uncertainty, their method of evaluation, sensitivity coefficients, standard uncertainties and covariances used in an uncertainty evaluation [9], which is a reduction of the description in the *International vocabulary of metrology* (VIM) [10]. Uncertainty budgets play an important role in the interpretation of measurement uncertainty as they provide an overview of

- the effects considered
- their values and standard uncertainties

- their impact on the standard uncertainty of the output quantity

Uncertainty budgets were not specifically introduced in ISO/IEC Guide 98-3:2008, but became popular with the publication of EA 4/02 [11, 12]. One of the issues with the simple tabular form used in EA 4/02 is that many of the uncertainty evaluations involve covariances between input quantities, which are not readily accommodated. In this report, the choice was made to stick to the tabular format and to append the contributions due to covariances to it. So, there is generally a “subtotal” from said contributions and a final total including the covariances. In both cases, the subtotal and final total are obtained using the law of propagation of uncertainty (LPU).

The evaluation of measurement performance along the supply chains for natural gas, biomethane and hydrogen is in many ways much more complex than the same analysis under well controlled conditions in a calibration laboratory or during off-site measurement. The conditions in supply lines can be harsh for the measurement equipment, e.g., the provision of hydrogen at a refuelling station. It is well known that the performance of flow meters is best when the flow rate is constant, and the more fluctuations, the poorer the performance. In that respect, the flow meters in refuelling stations have much more to endure than flow meters used for example for measuring the energy use of households.

This report does not aim to provide exhaustive uncertainty budgets for all scenarios. Instead, it focuses on illustrating methodological approaches and practical examples of how such budgets can be developed and applied in different parts of the hydrogen supply chain.

2 Methods

The methods used for evaluating measurement base on the GUM [5, 13–15] and standards like ISO 15112 [3] and requirement documents like OIML R137 [16], OIML R139 [17, 18] and OIML R140 [4]. The methods from the GUM have been extended to address the specific needs of analysing gas grid data [1]. These extensions have been compiled in a best practice guide [9]. Among these extensions are the integration of time series analysis in the totalisation of mass, volume and energy [19, 20], the use of the LPU on measurement models with compositions [21] and the evaluation of the dependence between subsequent indications in time series due to the use of the same instrumentation [9]. The GUM [5, 7, 13–15, 22] does not provide sufficient support for some of the applications relevant for metering in gas grids.

Methods for the evaluation and propagation of measurement uncertainty described in the GUM [5, 14] take a measurement model [13] as central point. From this measurement model, the input quantities are evaluated to obtain values and standard uncertainties (for use with the LPU) or probability density functions (PDFs) (for use with the Monte Carlo method (MCM)). A distinction is made between type A methods of uncertainty evaluation and type B methods [5]. The methods for propagating measurement uncertainty, originally developed for univariate, explicit measurement models [5, 14], were extended to cover multivariate and implicit models [15].

Most of the uncertainty budgets presented in this report are obtained using the LPU [5, 15], as this mechanism of propagating values and associated standard uncertainties is the de facto industry standard and used in many international standards [3, 23–31]. The measurement models used

are intrinsically non-linear however, so there are some risks associated with believing that the LPU without higher-order terms will always produce valid results [5, 14]. The emphasis in this work is on modelling the different effects (e.g., grid dynamics, instrumentation, calibration, precision under actual conditions) and incorporating these in the measurement model [20].

3 Results and discussion

3.1 Preamble

This chapter provides an overview of the case studies presented in Appendices A–C and summarizes the main findings. The appendices illustrate how the methods outlined in chapter 2 and described in the best practice guide [9] can be implemented in practice. Although the appendices do not include full uncertainty budgets in tabular form for every case, they demonstrate the methodology for evaluating measurement uncertainty under realistic operating conditions.

The case studies focus on different parts of the hydrogen supply chain:

- custody transfer of natural gas or hydrogen-enriched natural gas in the gas grid
- custody transfer of pure hydrogen in an industrial supply chain
- retail delivery of hydrogen at refuelling stations

3.2 Gas grid

Appendix A presents how to compute numerically the sensitivity coefficients and the covariance matrix when some of the variables involved in the measurement model have physical constraints. The example focuses on the determination of the uncertainty associated to the volume conversion factor including correlations due to the same gas composition measurement being used to determine the compressibility factor both at actual and at standard reference conditions. The correlation between the compressibility factor and the temperature and pressure values is also included. The procedure is generally applicable to any model including a variable subject to a constraint.

Appendix A includes also two complementary case studies addressing how signal processing can be applied in uncertainty evaluation for custody transfer. The examples studied are based on experimental data from the natural gas grid. However, the methodology is directly applicable to hydrogen systems and other dynamic processes.

The first part demonstrates how time-series analysis can be applied to quantify correlations in metered gas volume rate. This is done by applying auto-regressive moving average (ARMA) models to the stationary parts of the time series data. It is found that including such correlations increase the uncertainty calculated by statistical means (i.e., what is commonly referred to as type A uncertainty) in the totalised volume significantly compared to assuming independence between the measurements. This case study highlights the importance of including temporal correlation in uncertainty evaluations for custody transfer.

The second part focuses on the uncertainty analysis of the average superior calorific value based on time-sampled data. The method separates the input data into deterministic and random components, analyse them independently, and then evaluate their contribution to the combined uncertainty. Correlations in the random components are also included in the analysis. It is found that that the simple approach of calculating the uncertainty from the standard deviation of the mean can overestimate the uncertainty by nearly an order of magnitude.

3.3 Industrial supply chain

Appendix B presents an uncertainty analysis of a metering station in an industrial supply chain, based on hourly average experimental data over a typical month. The analysis uses the Monte Carlo method to propagate uncertainty from measured volume flow rate, temperature, pressure, and gas composition to combined uncertainty in energy flow rate. The uncertainty budget shows that the dominating source of uncertainty is the flow rate, followed by pressure. Temperature and gas composition has only a modest effect on the uncertainty. It is also shown how temporal correlations between succeeding measurements can be included in the uncertainty evaluation of totalised energy. Although the correlation coefficient was not estimated from data due to limited stationarity in the studied example, the results illustrate the impact of temporal correlations and the importance of determining the correlation coefficient accurately.

3.4 Refuelling station

Appendix C presents an overview of the metering at a Hydrogen Refuelling Station (HRS). The analysis is qualitative due to the lack of experimental data that could be obtained in this project. The chapter highlights the properties of the metering, and suggests how the methods developed could be applied to this application.

4 Conclusions

This report presents examples of metering uncertainty evaluations across various segments of the hydrogen supply chain, including the gas grid, industrial supply chains, and refuelling stations. The case studies illustrate how the methods described in the accompanying best-practice guide [9] can be implemented using real-world data.

The evaluations show that neglecting temporal correlations and deterministic structure in time-series data can lead to significant misrepresentation of uncertainty [1]. In the gas grid example, applying ARMA models to stationary subseries revealed that including serial correlation increased the calculated uncertainty by approximately 30%. In contrast, the calorific value example demonstrated that separating deterministic and random components using Savitzky-Golay filtering reduced the uncertainty estimate by nearly an order of magnitude compared to naïve averaging. These complementary findings highlight the importance of accounting for both correlation and signal structure. The report further shows how the GUM-based methods described in [9] can be applied to experimental data. This includes the use of Monte Carlo simulations to include

multivariate measurement models with dependencies between input quantities, the inclusion of both instrumental and temporal effects in the propagation of uncertainty, and the application of signal processing techniques to quantify uncertainty associated with totalisation and averaging. These examples demonstrate how the GUM-based methods can be adapted to practical hydrogen metering scenarios.

The report highlights that realistic uncertainty budgets require accounting for dependencies due to shared instrumentation, fluctuations in flow rates and gas compositions, as well as numerical integration effects. While the case studies are based on specific datasets and scenarios, the methods are general and applicable to other dynamic gas systems.

A Gas grid

This section presents an example on how to calculate numerically the covariance matrix for variables subject to physical constraints, such as the gas composition. This is particularly important for gas grids operators since the same measurement of the gas composition is used to calculate different quantities (most notably, the compressibility factor and the calorific value) necessary for the determination of the total energy.

Furthermore, two examples on how signal processing can be applied in uncertainty evaluation of dynamic flow, such as the flow through the gas grid, where supply and request keep changing over time. The examples are based on experimental data from the natural gas grid, but the methods are directly applicable for other dynamic processes such as custody transfer of hydrogen-enriched natural gas. The results obtained using the proposed methods are compared to the results that would be obtained using the current practice, i.e., assuming that the measurement results are mutually independent. This assumption of independence of the measurement results is in turned shown to be not applicable to measurements taken along the gas grid since significant correlations among measurement results have been found. The methods are presented separately but they could be combined by, e.g., applying the time series modelling to estimate the uncertainty of the random component of the input signal or by combining the type A uncertainty calculated using the time series analysis with the instrumental uncertainty obtained considering the correlations. A combination of the proposed methods is likely to result in a more accurate evaluation of the uncertainty and is subject to further research.

A.1 Volume conversion in natural gas metering

A.1.1 Summary

This example shows the uncertainty evaluation of the volume conversion in natural gas metering. This conversion of the gas volume measured under actual conditions to the corresponding gas volume at chosen reference conditions is a key element in the calculation of gas volumes. The example shows a rigorous evaluation of the measurement uncertainty associated with the factor K between a gas volume under reference conditions and a gas volume under actual conditions.

It also shows how the uncertainty from a measured composition, temperature and pressure can be propagated with an equation of state by evaluating the sensitivity coefficients needed numerically. Furthermore, it is shown how the composition affects the correlation coefficient between the compressibility factor at actual conditions and the compressibility factor between reference conditions when these are computed from the same composition. The LPU from ISO/IEC Guide 98-3/Supplement 2:2011 is used to propagate the measurement uncertainty as it is the simplest way to implement. A comparison is made between an approach that ignores the dependencies between the two compressibility factors

A.1.2 Introduction

In the metering of natural gas and related energy gases, including biomethane and blends of hydrogen and natural gas, the conversion of the gas volume as measured from actual to reference

conditions [3, Annex C] is a key step. In this example, the reference conditions of ISO 13443 [32] will be used, but the same procedure can be used with any other reference conditions. These conditions are a temperature of 288.15 K and a pressure of 0.101 325 MPa.

The conversion makes use of the gas law for real gases. Two compressibility factors are needed, one at actual and one at reference conditions. For the latter, ISO 6976 [25] is used, which takes on input a normalised composition of natural gas in accordance with ISO 6974 [23, 24]. The same composition is also used for the former compressibility factor, which is calculated using the GERG-2008 equation of state [33, 34]. The pressure and temperature during metering are measured with a known uncertainty.

A.1.3 Specification of the measurand

The measurand is the correction factor needed to convert a natural gas volume of a given composition from actual conditions (temperature and pressure) to standard reference conditions (reference temperature and pressure).

A.1.4 Measurement model

The formula for computing a gas volume at standard reference conditions (see, e.g., ISO 13443 [32]) takes the form [3, 4]

$$V_0 = V(p, T) \frac{p T_0 Z_0}{p_0 T Z}, \quad (1)$$

where V_0 denotes the real gas volume at standard reference conditions, p_0 the standard reference pressure, T_0 the standard reference temperature and Z_0 the compressibility factor at standard reference conditions. The standard reference pressure and temperature are without uncertainty, so there is no correlation with the measured pressure p and temperature T . The compressibility factors, if both calculated from the composition, are correlated through the gas composition. To use the law of propagation of uncertainty for calculating the covariance or correlation coefficient, an evaluation of the sensitivity coefficients is required. Generally, the compressibility factor at metering conditions will be calculated using an appropriate equation of state such as the GERG-2008 equation of state [33, 34].

The multivariate measurement model has as input vector

$$\mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x} \\ T \\ p \\ \mathbf{s} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (2)$$

where \mathbf{s} are the coefficients from ISO 6976 [25] for the calculation of the compressibility factor. The output vector of the measurement model takes the form

$$\mathbf{Y} = \begin{bmatrix} Z \\ Z_0 \\ T \\ p \end{bmatrix}. \quad (3)$$

The covariance matrix associated with the input variables \mathbf{V}_x takes the form of a block diagonal matrix

$$\mathbf{V}_X = \text{diag}\{\mathbf{V}_x, u^2(T), u^2(p), \mathbf{V}_s\}, \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{V}_x is given by equation (6) and \mathbf{V}_s a diagonal matrix holding the variances of the coefficients s_j appearing in the formula for Z_0 in ISO 6976 [25], i.e.,

$$\mathbf{V}_s = \text{diag}\{u^2(s_1), \dots, u^2(s_N)\}. \quad (5)$$

A.1.5 Input quantities

The input quantities are

- a vector \mathbf{x} holding the normalised amount fractions of N components in the natural gas being metered; the vector has an associated covariance matrix \mathbf{V}_x that is singular and meets the requirements of a composition [35, 36];
- the gas temperature T at the time of measurement;
- the gas pressure p at the time of measurement;
- the compressibility factor Z , calculated using the GERG-2008 equation of state [34];
- the compressibility factor Z_0 , calculated using ISO 6976 [25]

The normalised composition is given in table 1. The associated correlation matrix \mathbf{R}_x is shown in table 2. The covariance matrix \mathbf{V}_x can be obtained as [15, 3.21]

$$\mathbf{V}_x = \mathbf{D}\mathbf{R}_x\mathbf{D} \quad (6)$$

where

$$\mathbf{D} = \text{diag}\{u(x_1), \dots, u(x_N)\}$$

Table 1: Normalised composition of a natural gas containing 5 components, expressed in amount fractions (cmol mol^{-1})

Component	x cmol mol^{-1}	$u(x)$ cmol mol^{-1}	$u_{\text{rel}}(x)$
Nitrogen	3.280	0.022	0.67 %
Carbon dioxide	2.421	0.019	0.77 %
Methane	84.335	0.111	0.13 %
Ethane	6.587	0.044	0.67 %
Propane	3.378	0.110	3.27 %

The actual conditions are 300.00 K and 6.20 MPa. The standard uncertainty associated with the temperature is 0.20 K and that associated with the pressure is 0.05 MPa.

Table 2: Correlation matrix of the normalised composition

Component	N ₂	CO ₂	CH ₄	C ₂ H ₆	C ₃ H ₈
N ₂	1	0.0635	-0.0703	0.0367	-0.1543
CO ₂	0.0635	1	-0.0605	0.0320	-0.1341
CH ₄	-0.0703	-0.0605	1	-0.2531	-0.8782
C ₂ H ₆	0.0367	0.0320	-0.2531	1	-0.1609
C ₃ H ₈	-0.1543	-0.1341	-0.8782	-0.1609	1

A.1.6 Uncertainty propagation

The propagation of measurement uncertainty associated with the composition \mathbf{x} , temperature T , pressure p and the intrinsic uncertainty of the GERG-2008 equation of state is done using the LPU from ISO/IEC Guide 98-3/Supplement 2:2011 [15].

The uncertainty associated with the factor

$$K = \frac{pT_0Z_0}{p_0TZ}, \quad (7)$$

can be calculated using the LPU from ISO/IEC Guide 98-3:2008 [5, equation 13], recognising that the relevant sensitivity coefficients are given by [5, clause 5.1.6]

$$\frac{\partial K}{\partial p} = \frac{K}{p}; \frac{\partial K}{\partial T} = -\frac{K}{T}; \frac{\partial K}{\partial Z} = -\frac{K}{Z}; \frac{\partial K}{\partial Z_0} = \frac{K}{Z_0}, \quad (8)$$

the expression for the variance associated with K is

$$u^2(K) = \mathbf{C}_K \mathbf{V}_Y \mathbf{C}_K^\top. \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{C}_K is a row vector given by

$$\mathbf{C}_K = \left[\frac{-K}{Z}, \frac{K}{Z_0}, \frac{-K}{T}, \frac{K}{p} \right].$$

The covariance matrix \mathbf{V}_Y associated with the quantities Z_0, Z, T, p is formed as given in equation (2).

Whereas the propagating the uncertainty associated with the composition to Z_0 is well covered in ISO 6976 [25, Annex B], the same cannot be said from the calculation of Z . The GERG-2008 is quite an involved mathematical equation [33] and obtaining the partial derivatives necessary is quite involved if done through symbolic differentiation. With numerical differentiation however, the process is very straightforward and only requires a validated implementation of the equation of state that provides the value of Z , given the inputs (composition, temperature and pressure). Let this implementation of the GERG-2008 equation of state be denoted by f , then the partial derivatives with respect to the amount fractions can be obtained as follows.

First, construct an orthogonal matrix Q whose elements are given by the following expressions. For each column $j = 1, \dots, N - 1$, the first j elements are equal to

$$\frac{-1}{\sqrt{j(j+1)}},$$

and the following element is equal to

$$\frac{j}{\sqrt{j(j+1)}}.$$

The remaining elements are zero. For $N = 5$, using these formulæ,

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} -0.70711 & -0.40825 & -0.28868 & -0.22361 \\ 0.70711 & -0.40825 & -0.28868 & -0.22361 \\ 0 & 0.81650 & -0.28868 & -0.22361 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.86603 & -0.22361 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.89443 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (10)$$

The sensitivity coefficients c_j are obtained using the approximation

$$f'_q(\mathbf{x}_0) \approx \frac{f(\mathbf{x}_0 + h\mathbf{q}) - f(\mathbf{x}_0)}{h}, \quad (11)$$

where h is some constant, \mathbf{x}_0 the composition given in table 1 and \mathbf{q} is a column from \mathbf{Q} . Now, evaluate for each column j of \mathbf{Q} , denoted as \mathbf{q}_j

$$b_j = \frac{f(\mathbf{x}_0 + h\mathbf{q}_j) - f(\mathbf{x}_0)}{h},$$

where f is the implementation of the GERG-2008 equation of state providing Z . Then, the sensitivity coefficients are given by

$$\mathbf{c}^\top = \mathbf{b}\mathbf{Q}^\top, \quad (12)$$

where the elements of \mathbf{c} are the partial derivatives

$$c_j = \frac{\partial f}{\partial x_j}. \quad (13)$$

This numerical procedure considers that the amount fractions in a (normalised) composition are subject to a mathematical constraint [35, 36] and that these must not be varied one by one, as this process may lead to issues when evaluating f . A fuller discussion is given elsewhere [21, 37].

In the calculations, h is chosen to be 1% of the smallest amount fraction in the composition. This choice ensures that $\mathbf{x}_0 \pm h\mathbf{q}_j$ are valid compositions. According to ISO/IEC Guide 98-3:2008 [5, clause 5.1.3 NOTE 2], a perturbation in the order of a standard uncertainty would be adequate for applying the LPU. This choice of h does just do that.

The implementation of the GERG-2008 equation of state used in this example is that of TREND 5.0 [38] as an add-in for Microsoft Excel.

For the temperature and pressure, the process from the ISO/IEC Guide 98-3:2008 [5, clause 5.1.3 NOTE 2] can be used. So, evaluating the equation of state for $\mathbf{x}, T + \delta T, p$ and a second time for $\mathbf{x}, T, p + \delta p$, enables evaluating these two partial derivatives, which are approximated by

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial T} = \frac{f(\mathbf{x}_0, T + \delta T, p) - f(\mathbf{x}_0, T, p)}{\delta T}, \quad (14)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial p} = \frac{f(\mathbf{x}_0, T, p + \delta p) - f(\mathbf{x}_0, T, p)}{\delta p}. \quad (15)$$

In these expressions, \mathbf{x}_0 denotes the composition in table 1.

For the composition in table 1 and setting h equal to 0.01 times the smallest amount fraction in \mathbf{x} ($= 0.000\,242\,1 \text{ mol mol}^{-1}$, see table 3), the following compositions and compressibility factors are obtained (see table 3). From these, the compressibility factors at 300.0 K and 6.20 MPa were calculated (see table 4).

Table 3: Compositions used to calculate the partial derivatives with respect to the compressibility factor calculated using the GERG-2008 equation of state (mol mol^{-1})

Component	\mathbf{x}_0	$\mathbf{x}_0 + \delta \mathbf{x}_1$	$\mathbf{x}_0 + \delta \mathbf{x}_2$	$\mathbf{x}_0 + \delta \mathbf{x}_3$	$\mathbf{x}_0 + \delta \mathbf{x}_4$
Nitrogen	0.032 80	0.032 63	0.032 70	0.032 73	0.032 75
Carbon dioxide	0.024 21	0.024 38	0.024 11	0.024 14	0.024 16
Methane	0.843 34	0.843 34	0.843 54	0.843 27	0.843 29
Ethane	0.065 87	0.065 87	0.065 87	0.066 08	0.065 82
Propane	0.033 78	0.033 78	0.033 78	0.033 78	0.034 00

Table 4: Compressibility factors from the GERG-2008 equation of state and their distances with respect to the measured composition \mathbf{x}_0

Component	\mathbf{x}_0	$\mathbf{x}_0 + \delta \mathbf{x}_1$	$\mathbf{x}_0 + \delta \mathbf{x}_2$	$\mathbf{x}_0 + \delta \mathbf{x}_3$	$\mathbf{x}_0 + \delta \mathbf{x}_4$
Z	0.869 67	0.869 622	0.869 671	0.869 609	0.869 574
$\Delta Z/h$		-0.208 49	-0.007 94	-0.262 03	-0.408 8

From the quotients $\Delta Z/h$ in the ultimate row of table 4, using equation (12), the sensitivity coefficients can be computed (see table 5).

Table 5: Values of the sensitivity coefficients for the compressibility factor calculated using the GERG-2008 equation of state

Component	N ₂	CO ₂	CH ₄	C ₂ H ₆	C ₃ H ₈
Index i	1	2	3	4	5
$\partial Z/\partial x_i$	0.31772	0.02287	0.160571	-0.13552	-0.36564

Using equations (14) and (15), the sensitivity coefficients for temperature and pressure can be obtained. Setting $\delta T = 0.2 \text{ K}$ and $\delta p = 0.003\,72 \text{ MPa}$, the compressibility factor at a temperature $T + \delta T$ is 0.870 025. The compressibility factor at a pressure $p + \delta p$ is 0.869 601. From these and the compressibility factor at actual conditions (see table 4, column labelled \mathbf{x}_0), the sensitivity coefficients can be obtained, whose values are $-1.9326 \times 10^{-8} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ and that with respect to temperature 1.7609 K^{-1} .

For the compressibility factor Z_0 , also the sensitivity coefficients are needed. The expression for calculating the compressibility factor Z_0 is [25]

$$Z_0 = Z(T_0, p_0) = 1 - \frac{p_0}{101.325 \text{ kPa}} S^2 \quad (16)$$

where

$$S = \sum_{j=1}^N s_j x_j, \quad (17)$$

The expressions for the sensitivity coefficients can be obtained by developing the expressions for the total differentials [39], viz.,

$$dZ = -\frac{p_0}{101.325 \text{ kPa}} 2S dS, \quad (18)$$

where

$$dS = \sum_{j=1}^N x_j ds_j + \sum_{j=1}^N (s_j - \bar{s}) dx_j, \quad (19)$$

where $\bar{s} = N^{-1} \sum_{i=1}^N s_i$. The latter expression appreciates that the amount fractions of the composition are subject to a constraint [37]. Consequently,

$$\frac{\partial Z_0}{\partial x_j} = -2S(s_j - \bar{s}),$$

and

$$\frac{\partial Z_0}{\partial s_j} = -2Sx_j.$$

The partial derivatives with respect to the reference pressure and temperature are not required, as these are constants without uncertainty. That situation would be different had the model from ISO 6976 [25] been used to calculate a compressibility factor under actual conditions (which may be warranted at lower gas pressure [40]).

The covariance matrix associated with Y , V_Y , can be obtained using the LPU for multivariate measurement models as [15]

$$V_Y = C_X V_X C_X^\top, \quad (20)$$

where C_X denotes the sensitivity matrix. With the specifications of X and Y , the layout of C_X is fixed. On each row, the partial derivatives appear in the following order: amount fractions, temperature, pressure and the coefficients for Z_0 . The transpose of the sensitivity matrix reads

as

$$\mathbf{C}_X^\top = \begin{bmatrix} 0.317719 & 0.005618 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.02287 & -0.00026 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.160571 & 0.002837 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.13552 & -0.00195 & 0 & 0 \\ -0.36564 & -0.00624 & 0 & 0 \\ 1.76 \times 10^{-3} & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -1.93 \times 10^{-8} & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & -0.00331 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -0.00245 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -0.08521 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -0.00666 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -0.00341 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (21)$$

where the first column contains the partial derivatives for Z , the second for Z_0 , the third one for T and the right-most one for p . The order of the partial derivatives in the columns are those with respect to the amount fractions, the temperature, the pressure and the coefficients s_j from the formula from ISO 6976 for the compressibility factor.

The compressibility factors and their associated standard uncertainties are given in table 6.

Table 6: Compressibility factors from the GERG-2008 equation of state (Z) and ISO 6976 (Z_0) and their associated standard uncertainties

Quantity	Estimate	Std. unc.
Z	0.869 672	0.000 375
Z_0	0.997 448	0.000 044

The correlation matrix associated with \mathbf{Y} reads as

$$\mathbf{R}_Y = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0.011 & 0.940 & -0.192 \\ 0.011 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.940 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -0.192 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The correlation coefficient between Z and Z_0 is for this composition with associated uncertainty very small (0.011). The correlation coefficient between Z and T is strong (0.941) and the correlation between Z and p is small (and negative, -0.192).

A.1.7 Output

The value of $K = 67\,407\,308$ and the associated standard uncertainty $u(K) = 622\,683$, rounded, $K = 6.740 \times 10^6$ with $u(K) = 0.62 \times 10^6$. The relative standard uncertainty is 0.92 %.

The relative standard uncertainty associated with Z is 0.04 %, that associated with Z_0 is 0.0044 % (see table 6). Using equation (9), the relative standard uncertainty associated with K is 0.13 %.

Using the sensitivity coefficients from equation (8) and the variances associated with p , T , Z and Z_0 provides a relative standard uncertainty associated with K $u_{\text{rel}}(K) = 0.10\%$, notably smaller than that including the covariances between the input variables in equation (7).

A.1.8 Interpretation of results

At first glance, the difference between the two standard uncertainties computed for K appears small, but ignoring the dependencies between Z , p and T still constitutes an underrating of the measurement uncertainty by some 30%. Furthermore, this difference depends on the uncertainty associated with the input quantities (i.e., \mathbf{x} , p , T). Finally, it also depends on what the effect of the uncertainty associated with K is on the reporting of total volume or total energy. Generally, that uncertainty will be larger than the (relative) uncertainty calculated for K , so it can be justified to ignore said dependencies. This example provides the framework for making such an assessment. Whereas the data used in this example are deemed representative for fiscal metering of natural gas, the effect of correlations may differ from case to case, and is dependent on the data quality: the larger the uncertainties in the measurement of composition, temperature and pressure, the stronger the dependencies between Z , Z_0 , T and p become.

A second comment concerns the step of first forming V_Y (equation (20)) and then computing the squared standard uncertainty associated with K (equation (9)). These steps can be integrated by substituting the former into the latter:

$$u^2(K) = \mathbf{C}_K \mathbf{C}_X \mathbf{V}_Y \mathbf{C}_X^\top \mathbf{C}_K^\top. \quad (22)$$

When implementing this formula, the computational effort can be further reduced by first computing the matrix product $\mathbf{C}_K \mathbf{C}_X$, recognising that the transpose of this product is $\mathbf{C}_X^\top \mathbf{C}_K^\top$. The matrix multiplication thereby implements the chain rule of differentiation [39].

The partial derivatives for the GERG-2008 equation of state used in this example are not symmetric about the composition provided. ISO/IEC Guide 98-3:2008 and ISO/IEC Guide 98-3/Supplement 2:2011, presume using the symmetric partial derivatives, that is, using

$$f'_q(\mathbf{x}_0) \approx \frac{f(\mathbf{x}_0 + h\mathbf{q}) - f(\mathbf{x}_0 - h\mathbf{q})}{2h}, \quad (23)$$

instead of equation (11). The rest of the calculation remains exactly the same. Using (23) comes at the computational expense of $N - 1$ extra function calls to the function f (here the GERG-2008 equation of state) for the composition, and an additional two for temperature and pressure. The sensitivity coefficients symmetric about the composition \mathbf{x}_0 are shown in table 7. They are marginally different from the ones calculated previously (see table 5). The sensitivity coefficient with respect to pressure changes from $-1.9326 \times 10^{-8} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ to $1.9328 \times 10^{-8} \text{ Pa}^{-1}$ and that with respect to temperature from 1.7609 K^{-1} to 1.7637 K^{-1} . None of these differences between the values of the sensitivity coefficients affect the principal outputs for K as already shown for the asymmetric case in a meaningful way.

Finally, ISO 20765-2 [34, Table 10] states that predictions of the density of the gas phase for natural gas from the GERG-2008 equation of state come with a relative uncertainty of 0.10%. The compressibility factor is closely related to the gas density, so it would be appropriate to include this

Table 7: Values of the sensitivity coefficients for the compressibility factor calculated using the GERG-2008 equation of state symmetric about x_0

Component Index i	N ₂ 1	CO ₂ 2	CH ₄ 3	C ₂ H ₆ 4	C ₃ H ₈ 5
$\partial Z/\partial x_i$	0.31766	0.02285	0.16054	-0.13550	-0.36554

uncertainty component in the calculations. Assuming that this stated uncertainty is the half-width of a 95 % coverage interval, the relative standard uncertainty from the model would be 0.05 %. With a compressibility factor of 0.869 672, the absolute standard uncertainty is 0.000 435.

Integrating the model uncertainty into the covariance matrix associated with Y is straightforward, as this uncertainty component only affects the variance associated with Z . The covariances are not affected by this change (but the correlation coefficients are, though). The latter can be seen from, e.g., equation F.1 in ISO/IEC Guide 98-3:2008, which shows how the covariance between two quantities depends on the joint effects [5].

The value of K remains unchanged, but the standard uncertainty now becomes

$$u(K) = 92439,$$

and

$$u_{\text{rel}}(K) = 0.14\% \tag{24}$$

whereas the relative standard uncertainty ignoring the correlations increases to 0.11 %. The correlation matrix R_Y now takes the form

$$R_Y = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0.007 & 0.614 & -0.125 \\ 0.007 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.614 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -0.125 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}.$$

All correlation coefficients have become closer to zero, but judging the standard uncertainties calculated, they are still relevant.

When calculating a series of compressibility factors from the same equation of state (here the GERG-2008 equation of state), it is important to assume that the model uncertainty is correlated. This approach not only protects this assumption against underrating the measurement uncertainty, but it is supported by the fact that the model uncertainty is often of a systematic nature for a given data set.

A.2 Time series modelling of metered gas volumes

A.2.1 Summary

A generic treatment for the analysis of correlations in stationary time series by means of ARMA models is presented with an application to the volume flow rate measurement in the gas grid.

The so-calculated correlation is then included in the calculation of the uncertainty associated with the total volume and determined by statistical means using the LPU from the GUM. Results show an increase of approximately 30 % in the calculated uncertainty when compared to a model assuming that the data are independently distributed.

A.2.2 Introduction

Gas grid operators need to continuously monitor the quantity (and quality) of the gas flowing through the pipes to ensure that suppliers can feed the grid and users can draw gas from the grid. Measurement uncertainty is an important factor for operating the grid and can help operators to deal with imbalances in the grid. Standards [3, 6] and recommendations [4] describe the requirements for the measurements taken along the gas grid, including the evaluation of the measurement uncertainty. However, these standards assume that the measurement results can be treated as mutually independent. In the gas grid, where the flow is continuously adjusted to meet the demand, this is hardly the case [1].

Different factors can cause correlation among measurements results. This example constitutes a study on how to quantify the correlation between measurement results due to the inertia of the fluid. However fast the mechanical change to the grid configuration is performed (e.g., opening or closing of a pipe to favor a higher or lower flow rate in a particular area of the grid), the physical process of the fluid flow retains memory of its previous state due its inertia, which is the force due to the momentum of the fluid. Because of this, subsequent measurement results might be correlated.

This example treats the case of statistically stationary series of data. In the case of the gas grid, this might happen when no drastic changes, but only mild adjustments, are done to the flow rate for a certain period of time. As the gas grid is a dynamic environment, for a given period of time, the time series of flow rate measurement results might be stationary in an area of the grid but not in other areas. A more general approach allowing the treatment also of non-stationary time series of data is thus desirable and topic of ongoing research.

Since many transactions, e.g., in custody transfers, are done in terms of aggregated quantities, such as total volume or average calorific value, neglecting correlations among the measurement results may lead to an incorrect estimation of the uncertainty of the aggregated quantity and thus to costly errors when operating the grid.

A.2.3 Specification of the measurand

The measurand is the total volume of natural gas at normal conditions (i.e., 101.325 kPa, 0 °C, as specified in ISO 13443 [32]) recorded during a two-days time period at the metering station employing a turbine meter with a temperature and a pressure sensor.

A.2.4 Measurement model

The total volume at normal conditions V_{tot} is calculated as

$$V_{\text{tot}} = \sum_{t=1}^N V_t \quad (25)$$

where V_t is the accumulated volume at normal conditions recorded at the metering station during time interval $t \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ and N is the number of time intervals within the considered time period.

It is assumed that the series of volume measurements $\{V_t\}_{t=1}^N$ is the series of data that would be used when handling transactions for, e.g., custody transfer or billing. Thus, corrections for known errors (e.g., flow meter calibration curve) have already been accounted for. Since the measurement results are first converted to normal conditions and corrected for any known error (e.g., calibration error or drift), any residual correlation found in the data is not due to changes in the environmental conditions, nor to the instrumentation but to the inertia of the fluid flow.

A.2.5 Input quantities

The input quantities are the time series $\{V_t\}_{t=1}^N$ of accumulated volumes at normal conditions *after* application of any correction due to any known errors (e.g., indication error or drift). It is thus assumed that known systematic errors in the measurement instruments have already been corrected for.

These volume increments are computed from the volume flow rate measured at actual conditions, multiplied by the time gap Δt between two subsequent measurements. The volumes thus obtained are converted to normal conditions using the compressibility factors, temperatures and pressures at actual and normal conditions. This conversion is described in ISO 15112 [3, Annex C].

The volumes $\{V_t\}_{t=1}^N$ are assumed having a multivariate normal distribution. The time series analysis is used as type A method of uncertainty evaluation [41, clause 2.3] to obtain the parameters of this distribution.

A.2.6 Uncertainty propagation

A.2.6.1 Preamble

The uncertainty is propagated using the LPU as described in the GUM [41] though with some differences depending on the underlying assumptions on the measurement results. This example considers only the part of the uncertainty budget that is determined by applying statistical tools (time series analysis) to the data (i.e., type A uncertainty). Time series analysis is applied to obtain values for the correlation coefficients between pairs of indications in the time series.

Instrumental measurement uncertainty is thus not included in the time series analysis. It can be combined with the results of this uncertainty evaluation by expanding the measurement model accordingly.

A.2.6.2 Assumption of mutual independence

If the measurement results are treated as mutually independent, the LPU for independent input variables [41, Equation 5.10] is used to evaluate the uncertainty associated to the total volume. The standard uncertainty associated to each V_t $t \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ is given by the sample standard deviation s_{V_t} obtained as described in [41, Annex C.3.2], i.e.,

$$s_{V_t}^2 = \frac{1}{N-1} \sum_{t=1}^N (V_t - \bar{V})^2, \quad (26)$$

where

$$\bar{V} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t=1}^N V_t = \frac{1}{N} V_{\text{tot}}$$

denotes the mean of the time series. Replacing equation (26) into the LPU for independent input variables gives

$$u_{\text{ind}}^2(V_{\text{tot}}) = \sum_{t=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial V_{\text{tot}}}{\partial V_t} \right)^2 \text{Var}(V_t) = \sum_{t=1}^N 1 \cdot s_{V_t}^2 = N s_{V_t}^2. \quad (27)$$

A.2.6.3 Correlated measurement results

The correlation (and covariance) values between subsequent volume measurements are determined by fitting an ARMA model [42] to the data. An ARMA model of order (p, q) is a combination of an autoregressive (AR) process with p terms and a moving average (MA) process with q terms [43], and is given by

$$X_t = \alpha_1 X_{t-1} + \dots + \alpha_p X_{t-p} + Z_t + \beta_1 Z_{t-1} + \dots + \beta_q Z_{t-q},$$

where $\alpha_i \forall i \in \{1, \dots, p\}$ are the coefficients of the AR process, $\beta_j \forall j \in \{1, \dots, q\}$ are the coefficients of the MA process, and $\{Z_t\}$ is a purely random process. The random process Z_t could be compared to the model residuals in (classical) regression analysis. ARMA models are efficient and reliable tools when applied to series of data that are statistically (weakly) stationary. Note that statistical stationarity does not imply any sort of stationarity nor stability from a physical point of view.

The Augmented Dickey Fuller test (ADF) test is the most common statistical test used to check whether a given time series is stationary or not. If the null-hypothesis that a unit root is present in the time series can be rejected (at a predefined confidence level), the time series can be said to be stationary. In this example, the ADF test is used whenever a series of data is checked for stationarity, and the maximum lag to be included in the test is determined by minimizing the Bayesian information criterion (BIC). In Python, the ADF test is available as part of the `statsmodels` library [44].

A.2.6.3.1 Detecting stationary subseries Considering the dynamic behaviour of the gas grid, the time series of volume measurements recorded at a metering station is unlikely to be statistically stationary. This is indeed the case for the series of data analysed in this example. After applying the ADF test to the series of data, it was not possible to reject the null-hypothesis of the ADF test, and thus the series cannot be considered as stationary. In this case, the analysis by means of ARMA models should be limited to those parts of the time series that satisfy the stationarity requirement.

Change point detection methods [45] are a useful tool to automatically detect points along the time series where some of the statistical properties of the series change. Different change point detection methods use different criteria to determine the change points [45]. Thus it is possible that different methods determine different change points when applied to the same series of data.

In this example two change point methods are considered: binary segmentation (BinSeg) [46] and Pruned Exact Linear Time (PELT) [47]. BinSeg looks at changes in the mean of the series thus it works well to detect large changes in a given time series, though it may not detect more subtle changes. PELT instead monitors the empirical distribution of the data and it is more suitable than BinSeg to find more subtle changes, but it could also fragment the series too much. Therefore, care should be used when applying such methods. Note that the subseries determined by any change point method are not guaranteed to be stationary, therefore they should still be checked with the ADF test. BinSeg and PELT are available in Python via the ruptures library [45].

In this example, BinSeg and PELT detected the same change points along the time series of volume measurements recorded at the metering station (see figure 1 for a visualization of the splits determined by BinSeg). Application of the ADF test to the subseries from the beginning of the given time series until the first change point reveals that the series can be treated as stationary at the 95 % probability level. Thus in this example the correlation analysis by means of ARMA models is limited to that part of the series.

Figure 1: Change points determined by the BinSeg algorithm along the time series of the volume at normal conditions recorded at the metering station.

A.2.6.3.2 Fitting an ARMA model To fit an ARMA the order of the AR and MA processes need to be determined. This can be done by computing the (sample) auto-correlation function (ACF) and (sample) partial auto-correlation function (PACF). The ACF is a particularly useful tool to determine the order or (purely) MA processes, since the ACF is zero for terms at a higher distance than the order of the MA process. However, in case of (purely) AR or of mixed models (i.e., ARMA processes including both an AR and an MA component) it may display spurious correlations with higher order terms due to the autoregressive nature of the process. In this cases, more useful

insights can be obtained by computing the PACF. In Python, the (sample) ACF and PACF can be calculated using the `statsmodels` library.

It is important to note that, when applied to a physical system, AR and MA processes imply different properties of the system. In particular, AR processes imply that the quantity being analysed depends on its own previous value(s), while MA processes imply that the quantity of interest depends on the current and past values of a different quantity. Therefore, when choosing between AR and MA models, it is important to take into account the physics of the process and thus which model is more sensible from the point of view of the physics.

Figure 2: Time series of the volume at normal conditions measured at the metering station (top), the computed values of the (sample) ACF (mid) and of the (sample) PACF (bottom).

Figure 2 displays the stationary (sub-)series of volume increments at normal conditions together with its sample ACF and PACF. Both the ACF and PACF show significant correlation with lag 1 (i.e., with the measurement at the distance of one time interval). However, the ACF shows some residual structure for lags 2-5, while the PACF does not. If we consider the physics of the process, the correlation due to inertia would be between the current value of the volume with its own previous value. Therefore, an AR model would be better indicated to describe such phenomenon. As a consequence, in the next steps of the analysis the volume at normal conditions is modelled

as an AR process of order 1 (i.e., AR(1))

$$V_t = \mu_{V_t} + \alpha V_{t-1} + Z_t \quad (28)$$

where μ_{V_t} is a constant value, α is the coefficient of the AR process, and $\{Z_t\}$ is a purely random process.

Fitting equation (28) to the data (using the `statsmodels` library in Python), we obtained $\tilde{\mu}_{V_t} = 38596$ with associated standard deviation $s_{\tilde{\mu}} = 5328$, and $\tilde{\alpha} = 0.413$ with associated standard deviation $s_{\tilde{\alpha}} = 0.081$. The residuals of the fitted AR(1) model fit a normal distribution with zero mean and standard deviation $s_{Z_t} = 202$.

Note. In case of AR(1) models, the coefficient α is equivalent to the correlation coefficient between X_t and X_{t-1} . However, this is not the case for the general case of an AR process of order p . In fact, the coefficients of an AR(p) model can exceed 1 (in absolute value), which is not the case for the correlation.

A.2.6.3.3 Goodness-of-fit Fitting a model to experimental data does not imply that the model is a useful representation of the data. Particular care should be paid to avoid overfitting to obtain models with enough generalisability to fulfill the task at hand. Such properties of the model determine its goodness-of-fit. Models with a poor goodness-of-fit do not generalise well and are too sensitive to the noise present in the data. Therefore, they are not suitable for, e.g., uncertainty analysis.

Before proceeding with the uncertainty analysis, the goodness-of-fit of the fitted AR(1) model is evaluated. This is done by simulating 10 000 time series starting from the same initial value as the experimental data. The simulated series have then been used to determine a 95 % confidence interval (CI) and the behaviour of the individual simulation is compared to the starting data (see figure 3). The experimental data are within the 95 % CI and the individual series displays patterns similar to the experimental data. Thus, the model is an adequate representation of the data recorded at the metering station and may be used in the evaluation of the uncertainty associated to the total volume.

A.2.6.3.4 Inclusion of the correlation in the uncertainty calculation When considering correlated input variables, the LPU as described in [41, Equation 5.13] is used instead.

The standard deviation of each V_t $t \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ is determined taking into account that the volume is described by an AR model of order 1, i.e., equation (28). The variance of the AR(1) process given in equation (28) is calculated as (see [43])

$$\text{Var}(V_t) = \sigma_{V_t}^2 = \frac{\sigma_{Z_t}^2}{1 - \alpha^2}, \quad (29)$$

where σ_{Z_t} is the standard deviation of the random process Z_t and is estimated as the sample standard deviation of the residuals of the fitted AR(1) model. Note that from equation (25) it follows that $\partial V_{\text{tot}} / \partial V_t = 1 \forall t \in \{1, \dots, N\}$. Furthermore, equation (29) implies that a stronger correlation between measurements leads to a higher variance, while in case of no correlation (i.e., $\alpha = 0$) the case of independent input variables is recovered.

Figure 3: Plot of the experimental data, a simulated time series obtained with the AR model fitted on the experimental data, and the 95 % CI determined by 10 000 simulated time series.

The covariance between V_t and V_{t-1} is calculated as (see [43])

$$\text{Cov}(V_t, V_{t-1}) = \alpha \sigma_{V_t}^2, \quad (30)$$

and no correlation between V_t and V_{t-k} for $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $k > 1$ is considered. Replacing equations (29) and (30) in the LPU for correlated input variables leads to

$$\begin{aligned} u_{\text{cor}}^2(V_{\text{tot}}) &= \sum_{t=1}^N \left(\frac{\partial V_{\text{tot}}}{\partial V_t} \right)^2 \text{Var}(V_t) + 2 \sum_{t=2}^N \frac{\partial V_{\text{tot}}}{\partial V_t} \frac{\partial V_{\text{tot}}}{\partial V_{t-1}} \text{Cov}(V_t, V_{t-1}) \\ &= N \sigma_{V_t}^2 + 2(N-1) \alpha \sigma_{V_t}^2 \\ &= \sigma_{V_t}^2 (N + 2\alpha(N-1)). \end{aligned} \quad (31)$$

A.2.7 Output

The simulated time series that have been used to evaluate the goodness-of-fit of the proposed model, may be used also to calculate the uncertainties u_{ind} and u_{cor} using equations (27) and (31), respectively. The results are shown in figure 4 (left plot). The relative difference $(u_{\text{cor}} - u_{\text{ind}})/u_{\text{ind}}$ has also been calculated (see right plot in figure 4). The uncertainties calculated using the LPU for correlated input variables (equation (31)) are on average 28 % (with 95 % CI between 15 % and 38 %) larger than those calculated using the LPU for uncorrelated input variables (equation (27)). The distributions of the uncertainties calculated in the two methods overlap, however the distribution of the relative difference between the two uncertainties does not have negative values (the lower value recorded over the 10 000 simulations is larger than 0 %) thus, given a series of data, the inclusion of the correlation always lead to an increase of the uncertainty. The relative difference between u_{cor} and u_{ind} calculated on the data recorded at the metering station is approximately 30 %.

Figure 4: *Right*: plot of the distributions of the uncertainty values calculated on the simulated data using equation (27) (blue) and using equation (31) (orange). *Left*: plot of the distribution of the relative difference between u_{ind} and u_{cor} where u_{ind} is used as reference. In both plots, the results obtained using the data recorded at the metering station are displayed by a black dashed line.

A.3 Uncertainty analysis of the average superior calorific value

A.3.1 Summary

A case study is presented that focuses on evaluating the uncertainty associated with calculation of the average value of the superior calorific value based on the time sampled data. The analysis separates the input data into the deterministic and random components using a Savitzky-Golay filter. The deterministic component reflects systematic changes in gas properties, while the random component represents the data noise. Both components are analysed independently to calculate their associated standard uncertainties. The analysis also accounts for correlation between the samples of the random component. The study highlights that evaluating the calculation uncertainty simply as the standard deviation of the mean of the input data significantly overestimates the uncertainty predicted by the proposed method.

A.3.2 Introduction

Accounting for quantity or energy in gas trading usually involves calculation of the totalised or average values, which consequently also requires estimation of their uncertainties. The method applied in this case study uses a separation of time variations of the observed quantity into the deterministic and random components using the time-domain filtering (Savitzky-Golay filter), and subsequent separate uncertainty evaluation of both components. The details of the method used for the assessment of the uncertainty of the totalized/average value can be found in [9, 48, 49].

Here, this method is applied for the evaluation of the uncertainty of the average value of the superior calorific value $H_{s,i}$ under reference conditions. The time-sampled data were obtained for the natural gas at the metering station equipped with a gas chromatograph and with the sampling period of $t_{\text{samp}} = 15$ min. The time-sampled data, which serves as the input for the analysis, is shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Time-sampled data of the superior calorific value (input).

A.3.3 Uncertainty analysis of the average value

A.3.3.1 Average value and separation of the input signal

The average value is determined using the rectangle-rule numerical integration, written as follows for the observed data with the constant sampling period, $t_{samp,i} = t_{samp} \ i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$

$$\bar{H}_s = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N H_{s,i} t_{samp,i}}{\sum_{i=1}^N t_{samp,i}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N H_{s,i} = 40.8768 \text{ MJ/m}^3. \quad (32)$$

First, the input signal is separated into the deterministic and random components. The deterministic component is separated from the input data by applying Savitzky-Golay (S-G) filter of the 2nd order with the window length set to $N_{win} = 5$. The deterministic component together with the input data is shown in Figure 6. The random component is determined in the second step as the difference between the input data and the deterministic component (Figure 7). The deterministic component captures the changes in the superior calorific value due to deterministic changes in the properties of the gas metered. The random component describes the noise in the data set.

A.3.3.2 Uncertainty of the deterministic component

The deterministic component is decimated (downsampled) with the decimation factor n_{dec} , $n_{dec} = 1, \dots, N_{dec}$, and for each decimated component the average value $\bar{H}_{(s,det)}(n_{dec})$ is calculated. Figure 8 shows the average values of the decimated deterministic component of the superior calorific value with n_{dec} up to $N_{dec} = 4$ and the linear fit $\bar{H}_{s,det_{fit}} = an_{dec} + b$ which is obtained using the

Figure 6: Deterministic component after application of Savitzky-Golay filter ($N_{win} = 5$) shown together with the input data.

Figure 7: Random component of the superior calorific value.

least square approximation. The standard uncertainty of calculation associated with the deterministic component, u_{det} is estimated as:

$$e_{det} = \bar{H}_{s,det}(1) - \bar{H}_{s,det}(0) = 0.19 \text{ kJ/m}^3, \quad (33)$$

$$u(e_{det}) = s(\bar{H}_{s,det}(0)) = 0.035 \text{ kJ/m}^3, \quad (34)$$

$$u_{det} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{e_{det}}{\sqrt{3}}\right)^2 + u(e_{det})^2} = 0.12 \text{ kJ/m}^3, \quad (35)$$

where $\bar{H}_{s,det}(0) = b$ and $s(\bar{H}_{s,det}(0))$ is the standard error of the estimated of the parameter b .

A.3.3.3 Uncertainty of the random component

Figure 9 shows the ACF for the random component of the superior calorific value. The given ACF plot displays a clear structure with negative correlation values regularly alternating with positive values. Part of the correlation is due to the filtering method, however there might be also other factors causing correlation in the input data. As a consequence, we consider correlation effects in the evaluation of the uncertainty. The standard uncertainty of calculation associated with the random component, u_{ran} , is estimated by statistical analysis as the standard deviation of the mean and is calculated for the present case without and with consideration of the correlation between the samples:

$$u_{ran}^{(uncor)} = \frac{s(H_{s,ran,i})}{\sqrt{N}} = 0.25 \text{ kJ/m}^3, \quad (36)$$

$$u_{ran}^{(cor)} = \frac{s(H_{s,ran,i})}{\sqrt{N}} \sqrt{1 + \frac{2 \sum_{k=1}^{N_{cor}} (N_{ran} - k) \rho(k)}{N_{ran}}} = 0.30 \text{ kJ/m}^3, \quad (37)$$

where N_{cor} is determined by identifying the smallest k for which $\rho(k) > 0$ and $\rho(k+1) < 0$. As shown in Figure 9, N_{cor} equals 1 for the presented case.

Figure 8: Approximation of the average values of the decimated deterministic component ($N_{win} = 5$, $N_{dec} = 4$).

Figure 9: Autocorrelation coefficients of the random component of the superior calorific value ($N_{win} = 5$); leads to $N_{cor} = 1$.

A.3.3.4 Combined standard uncertainty

By taking both contributions into account, the combined standard calculation uncertainty without and with consideration of the correlation between the samples can be determined as:

$$u_{cal}^{(uncor)} = \sqrt{u_{det}^2 + u_{ran}^{(uncor)2}} = 0.28 \text{ kJ/m}^3, \quad (38)$$

$$u_{cal}^{(cor)} = \sqrt{u_{det}^2 + u_{ran}^{(cor)2}} = 0.32 \text{ kJ/m}^3. \quad (39)$$

In comparison, the standard uncertainty (inappropriately) calculated as the standard deviation of the mean of the whole input data, i.e., without separate evaluation of the deterministic and random components, gives:

$$u_A = \frac{s(H_{s,i})}{\sqrt{N}} = 2.94 \text{ kJ/m}^3, \quad (40)$$

which is almost ten times larger than the values in equations (38) and (39).

A.3.4 Discussion

The given estimates of the standard uncertainty in equations (38) and (39) are sensitive to the choice of the window length of the S-G filter (N_{win}) and the number of decimation steps considered (N_{dec}). Selecting $N_{win} = 10$ for this test case, the standard uncertainty considering correlation increases up to 0.8 kJ/m³ in comparison with the result for $N_{win} = 5$, which is still more than three times smaller than the estimate based on the standard deviation of the mean of the whole input data in equation (40). The conclusions of the analysis in [49], which are also based on analysis of synthetic signals, show that more realistic estimates of the calculation uncertainty can be expected at lower values of N_{win} and N_{dec} between 3 and 5.

The results show the advantages of the proposed procedure in terms of more realistic estimates of the calculation uncertainty, because the effects of the deterministic and random components are treated separately.

B Industrial Supply Chain

B.1 Introduction

Hydrogen has been used as a feedstock in various industries for decades, particularly in petrochemical and fertiliser production. A vast majority (90%) of the hydrogen is currently produced at sites adjacent to point of use. Transportation of larger amounts within industrial clusters is typically done via pipelines. Custody transfer of hydrogen relies on accurate measurements of both the quantity and quality of the gas, which are commonly determined using volumetric flow meters and gas chromatographs, respectively.

This section addresses uncertainty analysis related to energy metering in industrial supply chains. The focus is on how measurement data from flow meters, pressure and temperature sensors, and gas composition analysis are used to calculate energy content, and how the uncertainty in these calculations is influenced by instrumentation, operating conditions, and correlations in time series. The analysis is based on the principles of ISO 6976 and the ISO GUM, and illustrates how the Monte Carlo method can be applied to quantify uncertainty under realistic operating conditions. All calculations are performed using the software code developed in the Met4H2 project [50].

B.2 Measurands and measurement model

The gas flow rate at the metering station is measured with a 10” turbine flow meter. The metering station is also equipped with a gas chromatograph, temperature and pressure transmitters.

The measurands include the volume flow rate at actual conditions, temperature, pressure, and gas composition. The impurity levels are determined from gas chromatograph measurements, and the hydrogen content is calculated as the remainder after subtracting the measured impurities. All values are given as average values over 60-minute intervals.

Following the description and terminology in the best practice guide [9], the average energy flow rate in measurement period i is given by

$$\dot{E}_i = \dot{V}_{0i} H_{vi}, \quad (41)$$

where \dot{V}_{0i} is the average flow rate at reference conditions over the 60-minute interval, and H_{vi} is the corresponding average superior calorific value. In this example, the reference conditions are 0 °C, 101.325 kPa (normal conditions). The superior calorific value on a volume basis (H_v) is calculated from the gas composition using the method specified in ISO 6976 [25], as described in the best practice guide [9]. Note that in [9], the calorific value on a volume basis is denoted as \tilde{H} .

The volume flow rate at reference conditions is

$$\dot{V}_{0i} = \frac{p_i T_0 Z_{0i}}{p_0 T_i Z_i} \dot{V}_i \quad (42)$$

where V_i is the average measured volume flow rate at actual conditions, p is the pressure, T is the temperature, and Z_i is the compressibility factor. Parameters with subscript 0 refer to reference

conditions, whereas parameters without this subscript refer to actual measurement conditions. All values are averaged over the i 'th 60-minute measurement interval.

The relative uncertainty in energy flow rate ($\frac{u(E_i)}{E}$) can be calculated using the LPU.

$$\frac{u(E_i)}{E} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{u(p_i)}{p_i}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u(T_i)}{T}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u(Z_i)}{Z_i}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u(Z_{0i})}{Z_{0i}}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u(\dot{V}_i)}{\dot{V}_i}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u(H_i)}{H_i}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{u_{corr,i}}{E}\right)^2} \quad (43)$$

Here $u_{corr,i}$ represents the uncertainty contribution due to correlations between input parameters. As the compressibility factors (Z and Z_0) and the calorific value (H_i) are calculated from the gas composition, the uncertainties will be correlated. In this example the uncertainty contribution is calculated from the gas composition using the MCM, and correlations will therefore be included correctly in the calculations.

The accumulated energy over a period of N time intervals is

$$E(t_N) = \Delta t \sum_{i=1}^N \dot{E}_i \quad (44)$$

where $\Delta t = 60$ minutes.

Measurements at succeeding time steps are correlated. This correlation is represented by a correlation coefficient $r_{i,i+1}$ between two consecutive time steps,

$$r_{i,i+1} = \frac{u(E_i, E_{i+1})}{u(E_i)u(E_{i+1})}. \quad (45)$$

The uncertainty in the accumulated energy over the period is then calculated as

$$u^2(E(t_N)) = \sum_{i=1}^N u^2(E_i) + \sum_{i=1}^{N-1} r_{i,i+1} u(E_i)u(E_{i+1}) \quad (46)$$

B.3 Input quantities and associated uncertainties

The input quantities and instrumentation details were provided by a hydrogen supply chain operator. However, no specific information was available regarding the metering system's specifications, calibration procedures, or maintenance practices. Consequently, the uncertainty values used in the analysis are based on typical performance characteristics of state-of-the-art instrumentation for natural gas and reasonable assumptions.

Figure 10 shows the volume flow rate at actual conditions as a function of time. The maximum, transitional, and minimum flow rates of a typical 10" turbine meter designed for natural gas is indicated, although these limits may differ for hydrogen. It is observed that the flow rate is in the lower region of the meter's operating range, with a significant portion of the measurements falling below the meter's minimum flow rate.

The purity of the hydrogen gas is higher than (99.98% over the studied time frame). The main impurity is nitrogen. Other impurities are in the parts-per-million range and will not influence the energy calculations.

Figure 10: Flow rate at actual temperature and pressure conditions. The red lines show the flow meter's minimum, transition, and maximum flow rate.

Figure 11: Temperature and Pressure

Figure 11 presents the temperature and pressure profiles. Under normal operating conditions, i.e. when the flow rate is within the turbine meter’s operating range, the pressure varies from 15.5 bar(g) to 18 bar(g) and the temperature from 1.75 °C to 14.5 °C. During ramp-up/down phases, the variations are more pronounced.

Table 8 lists the input uncertainties ($k=2$) applied in this study. The values include the calibration and field uncertainties of the meters. These values are based on typical performance specifications for state-of-the-art instrumentation used in natural gas applications as no information about the applied instrumentation was available. However, the actual uncertainties and operating ranges for hydrogen systems are not yet well established and may differ significantly from those assumed here. Note that the flow-rate thresholds (referred to as $Q_{V,min}$, $Q_{V,t}$, and $Q_{V,max}$) are used solely as operational zones to parameterize measurement uncertainty in a GUM-based analysis. The percentage values assigned to each zone are expanded uncertainties ($k = 2$) adopted for modeling purposes only. They are not Maximum Permissible Errors (MPE), accuracy classes, or legal metrological limits as defined in OIML recommendations, and must not be interpreted as such. For flow rates below $Q_{V,min}$, the uncertainty is set to 2.4 %, although the true uncertainty may be significantly higher when the meter operates below its specified range. Nevertheless, the impact on the overall energy uncertainty remains limited because the corresponding flow volumes are small. All measurands represent averages over 60-minute intervals. The variability within the 60-minute intervals is not considered; it is assumed that the listed uncertainties are valid for these averaged values.

Table 8: Input uncertainties (95 % coverage probability) for the studied example

Input variable	Range	Uncertainty
T		0.2 K
p		0.07 bar
Q_V	$320 \leq Q_V \leq 1600$	0.6 %
	$80 \leq Q_V \leq 320$	1.2 %
	$Q_V < 80$	2.4 %
x_{N_2}		0.001 cmol/mol

B.4 Uncertainty calculation

The uncertainty calculations in this example are performed using the Monte Carlo method (MCM), which is in accordance with GUM [51]. A total of 1,000 iterations were used in the Monte Carlo calculations. The input parameters are volume flow rate, temperature, pressure, and gas composition (i.e. impurity fraction). Since the hydrogen content is determined as the remainder after subtracting the measured impurities, the normalisation procedure described in [9], chapter 8.4, is not required.

Both the compressibility factor and the gross calorific value are treated as input quantities in the measurement model used for the Monte Carlo analysis. Correlations between these parameters are inherently accounted for by the MCM, as they are derived from the same underlying gas composition.

Temporal correlations are included to calculate the uncertainty in totalised values. This is done by applying the correlation coefficient introduced in chapter B.2 (cf. 45 and 46).

B.5 Results and discussion

Table 9 shows the relative standard uncertainty budget ($k=1$) for a time interval when the flow meter is operating between the transition flow range and the maximum flow rate. The budget is calculated from the results of the Monte Carlo simulations. It is observed that the relative sensitivity coefficients for all input parameters are one, which is in agreement with equation (43).

Table 9: Relative uncertainty budget ($k=1$) based on measurements from April 9th 06.00 - 07.00

Variable	Value	Standard uncertainty (%)	Distribution	Sensitivity Coefficient	Uncertainty Contribution (%)
Z	1.010	0.050	Normal	1.00	0.071
Z_0	1.001	0.050	Normal	1.00	0.050
p	16.637	0.210	Normal	1.00	0.210
T	280.72	0.036	Normal	1.00	0.036
\dot{V}	788.44	0.300	Normal	1.00	0.300
H_v	12.759	0.007	Normal	1.00	0.007
Correlations					0.066
E	159218				0.369

The relative uncertainty contributions can also be visualized as bar plots as illustrated in Figure 12. This figure shows sensitivity plots of the relative expanded uncertainty ($k=2$) in energy flow rate when the flow meter is within its operating range. The two sub-figures correspond to flow conditions below and above the transition flow rate. The volume flow rate measurement is the primary source of uncertainty in both regions, followed by pressure measurements as the second-largest contributor. The uncertainty in gas composition, which influences on the compressibility factors (Z and Z_0) and the calorific value (H_v), has only a negligible effect compared to the contributions from flow rate and pressure.

Figure 13 presents the expanded uncertainty ($k=2$) in energy flow rate in absolute terms over the studied period. Although the relative uncertainty is high at low flow rates, the impact on the absolute energy flow rate uncertainty is modest. Nevertheless, the effect of operating the meter outside its specified range should not be overlooked, as the actual uncertainty may exceed the 2% assumed in this analysis.

Figure 14 shows the expanded uncertainty ($k=2$) in the accumulated energy over the one-month period for different values of the correlation coefficient r , assuming equal correlation between all succeeding time steps. This highlights the importance of accurately determining the temporal correlation coefficient when evaluating energy accumulated values. No attempt was made to apply the time series analysis method described in [9] to estimate the correlation coefficient, due to the limited presence of stationary periods in the flow rate data. As an alternative, the correlation coefficient could be derived through a detailed Type B evaluation based on the characteristics of the instrumentation. However, this approach would require more precise information than is

currently available—particularly regarding the flow meter’s performance and calibration history. Since much of the measurement uncertainty is systematic rather than random, a high correlation coefficient between successive measurements is typically expected.

Figure 12: Energy flow rate relative uncertainty sensitivity plot for flow rates (a) between $Q_{V,min}$ and $Q_{V,t}$ and (b) between $Q_{V,t}$ and $Q_{V,max}$

Figure 13: Absolute uncertainty in energy flow rate.

Figure 14: Accumulated uncertainty in energy over the studied period.

B.6 Summary

This example presented an uncertainty analysis of a hydrogen energy flow metering system for an industrial supply chain. The metering station is equipped with a 10" turbine flow meter, a gas chromatograph, and temperature and pressure transmitters.

Input parameters to the analysis include volume flow rate, temperature, pressure and gas composition, with uncertainties based on typical instrumentation. The measurands are averaged values over 60-minute intervals. The volume flow rate is converted to normal conditions and multiplied with the superior calorific value to calculate the energy flow rate. Accumulated energy over time is computed by summing energy flow rates, accounting for temporal correlations between measurements using a correlation coefficient.

The flow rates often falls below the flow meter's minimum operating range, introducing elevated uncertainty. The sensitivity analysis reveals that the dominant source of uncertainty is the flow rate, followed by the pressure. Gas composition has only a modest affect on the uncertainty. While relative uncertainty is high at low flow rates, its impact on absolute energy uncertainty is modest. However, operating outside the meter's range may lead to underestimated uncertainties. The analysis also highlights the importance of accurately modelling temporal correlation when evaluating accumulated energy.

C Refuelling Station

From a metrological point of view, the focus has been on the measurement system around the dispenser, i.e., on the delivery of hydrogen to public customers. This has been addressed in the EMPIR projects 16ENG1 MetroHyVe and the follow-up project 19ENG04 MetroHyVe 2. The topic of delivering gas to the HRS (i.e., B2B) has so far not been covered at the same depth.

From a survey from 2020, in the project MetroHyVe, 7 station operators were polled on questions concerning refuelling stations. When asked about their supply for hydrogen, it was found that hydrogen is either produced on-site by electrolysis (sometimes by solar panels) or delivered by gaseous tube-trailers [52]. Hydrogen is typically stored in buffer storage tanks but with significant variation in pressure, from 200 bar, 500 bar and even 800-1200 bar [52]. The car is filled in a tank-to-tank fuelling, i.e., there is usually no direct compression filling.

Figure 15: Constituents of a HRS measurement system for vehicles, with boundaries defining devices which are to be considered as part of the meter, or as part of the measuring system (as defined in OIML R139). Taken from [17].

To sell hydrogen to public customers, station manufacturers must comply with standards for resale of energy to individuals [53]. The relevant legal standard is OIML R139:2018 [17], [18]. The recommendation is mainly intended for compressed natural gas, but it also covers hydrogen gas.

In OIML R139, the meter and the measuring system and their borders are defined. It is shown in figure 15.

The technical standard outlining the fuelling protocol is SAE J2601 [54]. Protocols exist for various vehicle types:

- SAE J2601-1: Fueling Protocols for Light Duty Gaseous Hydrogen Surface Vehicles

- SAE J2601-2: Fueling Protocol for Gaseous Hydrogen Powered Heavy Duty Vehicles
- SAE J2601-3: Fueling Protocol for Gaseous Hydrogen Powered Industrial Trucks
- SAE J2601-4: Ambient Temperature Variable and Fixed-Orifice Fueling Protocols for Light-Duty Gaseous Hydrogen Surface Vehicles
- SAE J2601-5: High-Flow Prescriptive Fueling Protocols for Gaseous Hydrogen Powered Medium and Heavy-Duty Vehicles

The standards provide boundary conditions for both the pressure and temperature in the vehicle tanks. Hydrogen-powered vehicles have tanks that are made of either carbon fiber composite with aluminium liner (type III), or with polymer liner (type IV). Type IV tanks have a maximum temperature limit of 85 °C, which imposes an upper limit for the filling. This is illustrated in Figure 16. A H70 filling has temperature limits of –40 °C to 85 °C, and pressure limits 0.5 MPa to 87.5 MPa. To maintain the tanks within these boundaries, the station will adjust the mass flow rate of the gas based on a set of initial parameters, including the ambient temperature. For instance, as mentioned in the protocol [54]: “if a vehicle is fueled on a hot day, the initial CHSS¹ temperature may be warmer, so the station must fuel more slowly to ensure the CHSS does not exceed the maximum vehicle CHSS operating temperature”.

A filling profile following the the SAE J2601 standard is shown in Figure 17. Several observations can be made that illustrate a typical filling. Firstly, it is noted that the filling takes 204 s, which shows that the time scales in such fillings are short. With respect to the mass flow rate, it can be observed that it is transient, and obtains a prescribed maximum value in the first half of the full filling. With respect to the pressure, it does not start from 0 MPa, it is linearly increasing, and this comes from the fact that the Average Pressure Ramp Rate (APRR) is an important parameter that is set at the filling station. With respect to the temperature in the fuelling line, it can be seen that it quickly obtains the temperature with which the hydrogen gas is dispensed.

C.1 Measurand

The measurand for a HRS is thus the total mass of hydrogen delivered to an individual refuelling, i.e., their car or truck as recorded by the flow meter installed at the dispenser. Usually, a Coriolis mass flow meter is used to measure the delivered mass, which has the advantage of not being sensitive to pressure changes since it measures directly the mass flow rate. If a meter measuring in terms of volume is used instead, corrections due to temperature and pressure should be applied when calculating the total mass of hydrogen delivered.

C.2 Measurement model

The total mass of hydrogen m_{tot} delivered at a HRS is calculated as

$$m_{\text{tot}} = \sum_{t=1}^N m_t \quad (47)$$

¹Compressed Hydrogen Storage System, i.e., the tanks, relief devices, fittings, etc.

Figure 16: Typical boundary conditions set in SAE J2601. Maximal gas temperature in the storage tank of the vehicle and the maximum operating pressure are shown as limits on the right and left portions of the graph. Maximum density is shown as a black line and is an additional boundary condition.

where m_t is the accumulated mass recorded at the dispenser during time interval $t \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ and N is the number of time intervals within the considered time period.

C.3 Input quantities

The input quantities are the time series $\{m_t\}_{t=1}^N$ of accumulated mass.

C.4 Uncertainty calculation

In most industrial settings, the LPU from [41] is used either with or without correlations depending on the underlying assumptions. Since the measurand is an aggregated quantity (i.e., the total mass of the gas delivered), its associated uncertainty is influenced by several factors highlighted in [1], i.e., correlation due to the same instrumentation used to record all the measurement results in the time series, numerical approximation of the integral by a finite sum and temporal effects. Due to the lack of experimental data that could be used for the analysis, here we simply highlight how the methods developed could be applied also to this application.

Figure 17: Typical simulated H70 (700 bar) filling profile following SAE J2601, with a pre-cooling to -40 °C. In blue: mass flow rate [g/s], in red: temperature [°C] and in green: pressure in vehicle tank [MPa].

C.4.1 Temporal effects

Considering that the flow of hydrogen is not continuous but the measurements start from a no-flow condition up to a preset maximum flow rate, inertia is expected to play a role and thus subsequent measurement results are expected to be mutually correlated. Time series analysis could be used to estimate this source of correlation. However, considering the typical filling profile, the time series analysis based on ARMA processes for stationary time series presented for the hydrogen enriched natural gas case is likely not applicable to this case, and a methodology that allows to analyse non stationary time series is required. Furthermore, temporal effects might be even more relevant in HRS where the flow meter is downstream of the heat exchanger and thus more subject to temperature changes.

C.4.2 Totalization uncertainty

The total mass of hydrogen delivered is an approximation of the area under the filling profile. As such, the finite number of measurement points available to approximate such profile influences the uncertainty associated to the measurand. This source of uncertainty could be estimated by separating in the recorded signal the deterministic from the random component by means of the Savitzky-Golay filter, as shown in subsection A.3 for the average calorific value.

C.4.3 Instrumental correlation

Finally, given a breakdown of the uncertainty budget of all the meters involved in the measurement procedure (e.g., the flow meter and the temperature and pressure sensors), the correlation coefficients due to the instrumentation can be readily calculated and incorporated in the uncertainty budget of the total mass.

C.4.4 Summary

This example presented a hydrogen refuelling station case. As experimental data was not available, only a qualitative analysis was possible. The metrological properties of the personal vehicle filling was described. The input quantity is the time series of the accumulated mass.

In the uncertainty calculation, several factors are expected to contribute and may be handled by the tools and methods developed in this project. Among them are correlations arising due to the same instruments recording the measurements in the time series, and errors due to the estimate of the totalization. Another factor which is expected and relevant, but which may *not* be suitably handled by the methods presented, is temporal effects. Due to the rapidly changing profile stationary time series analysis will not be applicable.

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